

Controlling for maximum rate of environmental change as described in Supplementary Material (S1)

File made using *Wolfram Mathematica*

The original scaled function describing environmental change is:

$$y = \text{eta} * (t / \text{tmax})^{\text{exp}}$$

$$\text{eta} \left(\frac{t}{\text{tmax}} \right)^{\text{exp}}$$

For decelerating environmental change, we want to transform the function so that the part of the curve at which the slope is eta/tmax (which the slope of the linear function for environmental change) occurs at t=0.

The transformation in the t-axis direction is found by finding the value of t for which the first derivative is equal to eta/tmax, which provides a solution:

$$s = \text{Solve}[(D[y, t]) == \text{eta} / \text{tmax}, t]$$

Solve::ifun: Inverse functions are being used by Solve, so some solutions may not be found; use Reduce for complete solution information. >>

$$\left\{ \left\{ t \rightarrow \left(\frac{1}{\text{exp}} \right)^{\frac{1}{-1+\text{exp}}} \text{tmax} \right\} \right\}$$

Then the suitable transformation in the y-axis direction is found by substitution:

y /. s

$$\left\{ \text{eta} \left(\left(\frac{1}{\text{exp}} \right)^{\frac{1}{-1+\text{exp}}} \right)^{\text{exp}} \right\}$$

These terms are found in Supplemental equation S1.

For accelerating environmental change, we want to compress the function so that the part of the curve at which the slope is eta/tmax (which the slope of the linear function for environmental change) occurs at t=tmax. We find a suitable compression factor by solving:

$$v = (\text{Solve}[(D[y, t]) == x / \text{tmax}, \text{eta}] /. t \rightarrow \text{tmax})[[1]]$$

$$\left\{ \text{eta} \rightarrow \frac{x}{\text{exp}} \right\}$$

This factor (with x standing in here for η) is found in Supplementary Eq. S2.

This function plots a linear, decelerating, and accelerating, respectively, function controlling for

maximum rate of environmental change.

```

Clear[f];
f[x_, expDec_, expAcc_, tmax_] := f[x, expDec, expAcc, tmax] =
  Show[ListPlot[Table[eta * (time / tmax)^exp /. eta -> x /. exp -> 1, {time, 0, tmax}],
    PlotStyle -> Red],
    ListPlot[Table[(((eta * ((time + (1/exp)^(1/(1+exp)) * tmax)) / tmax)^exp) - (y /. s)) /. eta -> x /.
      exp -> expDec)[[1]], {time, 0, tmax}]],
    ListPlot[Table[(((eta / exp) * (time / tmax)^exp) /. eta -> x /. exp -> expAcc),
      {time, 0, tmax}], PlotStyle -> Green]]

```

Below is a sample of environmental trajectories controlling for maximum environmental change. The slope of the linear (red) curve is the slope of the decelerating (blue) curve at time=0 and of the accelerating (green) curve at t=5000.

```
f[75, 0.1, 5, 5000]
```

